

D5.3

Document on quality criteria for data

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Abstract [200 – 300 words, for dissemination]

Quality curated datasets related to nanomaterials safety evaluation are needed for sensitivity analysis and performance testing of the risk assessment models/tools chosen to be evaluated for inclusion in the caLIBRAte System of Systems framework. Recent reviews on quality aspects for toxicological studies in general and specifically for nanomaterials provided an excellent basis for defining a set of quality criteria that will aid the project in the selection of appropriate datasets. Quality-related terms, including reproducibility, repeatability, reliability, uncertainty, relevance and completeness, have been explained to detail and key quality parameter relationships depicted based on the recent review by Marchese Robinson et al, 2016. Furthermore, annexes summarize existing quality evaluation initiatives related to nanomaterials, required input parameters for selected risk assessment models, as well as minimum information checklists for both physicochemical characterization and environmental health and safety data. The proposed caLIBRAte quality assessment method involves scoring of relevance, reliability and completeness of data, including the possibility of addressing the entities in flexible order and related to a developing and increasingly precise nanomaterials ontology. The overall concept sets a basis for data curation that is aimed to guide the efforts within caLIBRAte and beyond. Future refinement of the proposed assessment parameters and workflow are likely to occur, as the basis for quality rating and fusion of diverse disparate data types and “Big Data” generally represents a young and recent science discipline. Additionally and significant to this deliverable, the definitions of quality and completeness should be expected to evolve in parallel to an increasing scientific understanding.

Keywords [up 5 keywords should be sufficient]

Data quality, relevance, reliability, completeness, curation

Description of Deliverable

Description of the deliverable at hand (D5.3) in the DoA: Document on quality criteria for data - This deliverable will describe quality criteria for data. The data requirements defined in a previous deliverable (D5.1) will form the basis of the methodology of quality labelling.

D5.3 is related to Task 5.2, which is described in the DoA as (bold text is relevant to D5.3): Data will be harvested through important collaboration with SUN, GUIDEnano, MARINA, NanoSolutions, NANoREG, NANoREG II, ENRHES and NanoMile. These collaborations will allow sharing of information on testing protocols, NM characterisation, data on key toxicity end points both in vivo and in vitro (also based on WP4), as well as on experiences and plans on attempts to group nanomaterials (OECD, ECHA, NanoMile, NanoReg II). Partners of caLIBRAte involved in the other projects will ensure the collaboration and support on exchange of information and data. Additionally, we will also make contact with national contact points to establish links to research projects funded through national sources, which represent a large resource of funded work in nanosafety. Key programs are identified in the UK, Germany, The Netherlands, France, and Italy. The gathering of data will be building on existing ontologies that are incorporated in a data warehouse, using the knowledge and experience from earlier projects (e.g. eNanoMapper and NANoREG I & II). Both the databases as well as the algorithms will be prioritized taking into account for instance the time needed for implementation and realized in that order. The databases to be included should have an accessible API (application program interface) defined. The validation algorithms from WP2, T2.5 (to be run in this platform) should be implemented in a single programming language (preferably R) or executable from the command line on a Linux operating system. Legally protected, restricted or otherwise unavailable data will not be pursued in this task. The resulting database or data warehouse will not be a static one, but will be open for integration of data from future projects. **[Text particularly relevant to the current deliverable] Data quality will be a key issue, since the use of high quality data in the performance testing and calibration of tools and models will result in an improved risk assessment. Quality criteria for data will be developed or, where appropriate, collected from previous initiatives. The minimum set of data requirements previously defined in task 5.1 will form the basis of the methodology of quality labelling. If the imposed criteria are not met, incomplete datasets can still be included in the studies,**

but will be labelled as low quality and be analysed with caution. The aim will be to identify the largest possible set of studies that can provide fully reliable and supplementary data for risk analysis.

Description of D5.1 in the DoA: Report on data requirements and listing of available data collections - A document containing 1) the description of data requirements to guarantee data comparison across laboratories and to allow an overall estimation of data quality and 2) an overview and description of existing databases useful for risk assessment (information gathered under milestone 1 of WP5).

Deviations from workplan in DoA and corrective actions

The deliverable is delayed by two months due to the delay of D5.1, which forms the basis for the deliverable at hand (see above). Detailed description of the delay of D5.1 can be found in the respective deliverable.

The deliverable will be updated with new information where appropriate. For example updates of D5.1 are to be expected upon the selection of new ERA models and with the identification of additional endpoints required for the “next generation” predictive models in WP2 and 3. Furthermore, novel information relevant to the quality assessment is expected to be available from the EU FP7 project GUIDEnano within the year.

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1. Introduction

Task 5.2 in caLIBRAte aims at collecting high quality data to be stored in the caLIBRAte database and used for the performance testing of designated risk assessment (RA) models/tools. The task builds on work performed in Task 5.1, which analysed and listed the data requirements for the data to be stored, provided an overview of existing data collections (both reported in D5.1), and established the caLIBRAte database (described in D5.2). The main objective of Task 5.2 is to gather data from the existing data collections, assess and label the quality of the data, and store it in the caLIBRAte database. The main objective of the work leading to the current deliverable was to develop a clear set of quality criteria and a quality labelling method for the data collected within caLIBRAte.

Curated high quality data is essential to understanding and predicting manufactured nanomaterials' (NM) behavior, and thereby to be able to reliably use existing data within various risk assessment approaches, such as grouping and read-across. Assessing data quality within the nanosafety field is challenged by its multidisciplinary nature, where highly diverse fields of research have traditionally handled, stored and annotated their data in widely different ways. A recent rise in the realization of the importance of quality has triggered discussion on complex topics such as uncertainty, reproducibility and interoperability, which are now being tackled within the community, to address viable solutions for complex data quality assessment (Hendren et al, 2015). Examples are taken from other fields such as chemical toxicology and drug development, and especially the bioinformatics community, which provides a concrete demonstration of the value that harmonization of large and disparate datasets can bring to the broader scientific community (Sansone et al. 2012; Hendren et al. 2015). Implementation of well-defined curation workflows plays a role in maximizing the effectiveness of data gathering and sustainability of common resources, and in addition provides information about standardisation possibilities, common bottlenecks and leverage points that benefit the community (Powers et al. 2015).

As reviewed by Marchese Robinson et al (2016) various schemes for scoring/categorising NM data (in part) according to their quality have been proposed in recent years. The authors particularly discuss how to assess the quality of NM data and pointed out the equally important aspect of data

completeness, i.e. whether a dataset is sufficiently complete to be fit for the intended purpose (Marchese Robinson et al, 2016). Data quality and completeness are defined as being highly interrelated, but nevertheless distinct and may require separate assessment approaches (Figure 1). The concept of data quality applies to a single datum (i.e. a single data point) or a single “finding”, taking into account its associated metadata. A “finding” might be a conclusion derived from analysis of a set of raw or processed data and the “metadata” associated with that finding might include these data. Quality is strongly related to the reliability of the data, i.e. the level of trustworthiness, reproducibility, repeatability, uncertainty and error (Figure 1), which can be associated with standard testing according to Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) or standard operating procedures (SOPs). However, the uncertainty regarding SOPs, which might miss novel endpoints or be based upon assumptions regarding the mode of action that are not applicable to some NMs, is also being considered (Marchese Robinson et al. 2016). In contrast, the concept of data completeness applies to a dataset and its associated metadata. The number of data points of a specific kind (e.g. physicochemical characterization of NMs in parallel with toxicity assessment) may be a completeness criterion in specific contexts if a given number of data points are required to achieve a specific aim. The dependence of both quality and completeness upon metadata is not entirely the same. For example, metadata (e.g. related to the NM identity and experimental conditions) are required to determine the relevance of the data for answering a specific question. The relevance of data for answering a specific question affects the completeness of the data, since only relevant data should be counted when evaluating completeness, but not the quality of a datum or finding.

Figure 1. The quality and completeness of NM data are viewed as overlapping, yet distinct, concepts. Completeness applies to a dataset and its associated metadata. The concept of data quality can be seen as being related to reliability and applies to a single datum (i.e. a single data point) or a single “finding” (i.e. a conclusion derived from analysis of a set of raw/processed data), taking into account its associated metadata. PCC = physicochemical characterization. (Figure adapted from Marchese Robinson et al, 2016).

Similarly, when evaluating available information on chemicals in the context of risk assessment under the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) the three elements

of relevance, reliability and adequacy are included in the assessment of data quality. The terms were defined by Klimisch et al. (1997), who also developed one of the most commonly used methods for quality assessment within toxicology. The Klimisch scoring method assesses the reliability of toxicological studies and assigns them to one of four categories. Table 1 lists the definitions of the quality assessment-associated terminology introduced above.

Table 1. Definitions of quality assessment-associated terminology.

Description	Details (partly quoted from the references)
Curation ¹	The steps commonly included in data curation workflows include: 1) Identification of publications/datasets relative to the intended scientific purpose; 2) Preliminary assessment of data quality and completeness of selected in-house or publication data for data quality and completeness (with assumption that any in-house data would be pre-identified within a project prior to the wider publication search referred to in Step 1); 3) Data extraction of raw data and/or data from the publication; 4) Communication with publication authors/data generators; 5) Curation of data into the intended repository and/or data format (e.g. Excel templates, ISA-TAB-Nano) leveraging common data elements (CDEs) from relevant ontological resources (e.g. eNanoMapper ontology [ENM]); 6) review of curated data for data quality and completeness; 7) Release of curated data; 8) Update of curated data as additional information is received from the authors. Though shown here in linear fashion, the order of these common steps for an individual process may be flexible and iteration is expected. The specific steps in a workflow may also differ across repositories depending on the intended purpose of the nanomaterial resource.
Relevance ²	Relevance covers the extent to which data and tests are appropriate for a particular hazard identification or risk characterisation.

Reliability ^{2, 3}	<p>Reliability is strongly related to data quality and is based on evaluating the inherent quality of a test report or publication relating to preferably standardised methodology and the way the experimental procedure and results are described to give evidence of the clarity and plausibility of the findings.</p> <p>Quality may be considered a measure of the potential usefulness, clarity, correctness and trustworthiness of data and datasets. However, there is no definitive consensus regarding exactly how data quality should be defined in the nanoscience, or wider scientific, community.</p> <p>Data quality may be considered dependent upon the degree to which the meaning of the data is “clear” and the extent to which the data are “plausible”. In turn, this may be considered to incorporate (aspects of) data completeness. For example, data quality may be considered to be (partly) dependent upon the “reproducibility” of data and the extent to which data are reproducible and their reproducibility can be assessed will partly depend upon the degree of data completeness in terms of the, readily accessible, available metadata and raw data. As well as “reproducibility”, data quality may be considered to incorporate a variety of related issues. These issues include systematic and random “errors” in the data, data “precision” (which may be considered related to notions such as “repeatability” or “within-laboratory reproducibility”), “accuracy” and “uncertainty”. (As indicated in the original review by Marchese Robinson et al. (2016), different scientists may provide somewhat different definitions for these concepts. These concepts may be considered in a qualitative or quantitative sense.) Data quality may also be considered to be dependent upon the “relevance” of the data for answering a specific question, although data “relevance” might be considered an entirely distinct issue from data quality (see above). In the context of data curation, not only the quality of the original experimental data needs to be considered but also quality considerations associated with curated data. Quality considerations associated with curation include the probability of transcription errors and possibly whether a given dataset, structured according to some standardised format (e.g. XML based), was compliant with the rules of the applicable standardised format (e.g. as documented via an XML schema). Such compliance, amongst other possible aspects of data quality, could be determined using validation software.</p>
Adequacy ²	<p>Adequacy defines the usefulness of data for hazard/risk assessment purposes. Where there is more than one study for each endpoint, the greatest weight is attached to the studies that are the most relevant and reliable. For each endpoint, robust summaries need to be prepared for the key studies.</p>

Completeness ³	<p>The completeness of data and associated metadata may be considered a measure of the availability of the necessary, non-redundant (meta)data for a given entity e.g. a nanomaterial or a set of nanomaterials in the context of nanoscience. However, there is no definitive consensus regarding exactly how data completeness should be defined in the nanoscience, or wider scientific, community. Indeed, metadata availability may be considered an issue distinct from data completeness.</p> <p>Data completeness may be considered to include, amongst other kinds of data and metadata, the extent of nanomaterial characterization, both physicochemical and biological, under a specified set of experimental conditions and time points. It may also encompass the degree to which experimental details are described, as well as the availability of raw data, processed data, or derived data from the assays used for nanomaterial characterization. Data completeness may be considered to be highly dependent upon both the questions posed of the data and the kinds of data, nanomaterials and applications being considered. Data completeness may be defined in terms of the degree of compliance with a minimum information checklist (see below).</p> <p>However, when estimating the degree of data completeness, it should be recognized that this will not necessarily be based upon consideration of all independent variables which determine, say, a given result obtained from a particular biological assay. This is especially the case when data completeness is assessed with respect to a predefined minimum information checklist. Precise definitions of completeness may evolve in tandem with scientific understanding.</p> <p>Note! In REACH, completeness is described as “the comparison between the available information and the information that is required under the REACH registered for the tonnage level of the substance” (ECHA, 2008).</p>
Minimum information checklist ³	<p>Minimum information checklists might otherwise be referred to as minimum information standards, minimum information criteria, minimum information guidelines or data reporting guidelines etc. These checklists define a set of data and metadata that “should” be reported – if available – by experimentalists and/or captured during data curation. Again, the precise set of data and metadata that “should” be reported may be considered to be highly dependent upon both the questions posed of the data and the kinds of data, nanomaterials and applications being considered. There are two possible interpretations of the purpose of these checklists: (1) they should be used to support assessment of data completeness (see above); (2) data should be considered unacceptable if they are not fully compliant with the checklist.</p>

¹ Powers et al. 2015

² Klimisch et al. 1997

³ Marchese Robinson et al. 2016

As a further refinement of the Klimisch scoring system, the software-based tool “ToxRTool” (**Toxicological data Reliability Assessment Tool**) was developed within the context of an ECVAM (European Centre for the Validation of Alternative Methods) funded project to provide comprehensive criteria and guidance for evaluations of the inherent quality of toxicological data for human risk assessment, making the decision process of assigning reliability categories more transparent and more harmonised (Schneider et al. 2009). The ToxRTool currently evaluates *in vivo* and *in vitro* data and is applicable to various types of experimental data, endpoints and studies, which are assigned to Klimisch categories 1, 2 or 3 (Table 2). The 4th category, which refers to secondary literature and handbooks, was not included in the tool. The tool comprises a list of 21 criteria for *in vivo* studies and 18 criteria for *in vitro* studies grouped into 5 groups: test substance identification, test system characterisation, study design description, study results documentation and plausibility of study design and results. A score is calculated based on the total number of criteria that are met, which are assigned a value of 1. Criteria that are not met are assigned a value of 0. In addition, 8/21 criteria for *in vivo* studies, and 6/18 criteria for *in vitro* studies are weighted and referred to as “red criteria”, which need to be met for the study/dataset to be placed in category 1 or 2. If one or more of the “red criteria” are not met, then category 3 is automatically assigned regardless of the total score.

Table 2. Klimisch score categories.

Score	Description	Details (quoted from Klimisch et al. 1997)
1	Reliable without restriction	"This includes studies or data from the literature or reports which were carried out or generated according to generally valid and/or internationally accepted testing guidelines (preferably performed according to GLP*) or in which the test parameters documented are based on a specific (national) testing guideline (preferably performed according to GLP) or in which all parameters described are closely related/comparable to a guideline method"

2	Reliable with restriction	"This includes studies or data from the literature, reports (mostly not performed according to GLP), in which the test parameters documented do not totally comply with the specific testing guideline, but are sufficient to accept the data or in which investigations are described which cannot be subsumed under a testing guideline, but which are nevertheless well documented and scientifically acceptable."
3	Not reliable	"This includes studies or data from the literature/reports in which there are interferences between the measuring system and the test substance or in which organisms/test systems were used which are not relevant in relation to the exposure (e.g., unphysiologic pathways of application) or which were carried out or generated according to a method which is not acceptable, the documentation of which is not sufficient for an assessment and which is not convincing for an expert judgment."
4	Not assignable	"This includes studies or data from the literature, which do not give sufficient experimental details and which are only listed in short abstracts or secondary literature (books, reviews, etc.)."

*Note that GLP does not ensure that data is reliable per se, but refers to a high level of recording and archiving

Although the ToxRTool has been evaluated as valuable largely due to the transparency of the assessment performed, it has also been criticized due to the tendency for subjective assessments, and recommendations for refinement of the tool have been made (Segal et al. 2015). For the assessment of nanotoxicological data an extended 2-step method was described by Card & Magnuson (2010). The method involves evaluation of both the reliability of a given study and the completeness of the physicochemical characterization of the tested NM(s). The first step uses the ToxRTool to rank the reliability of the study based on adequacy of design and documentation of methods, materials, and results, providing a "study score". The second step determines the completeness of physicochemical characterization of the NM(s) assessed within the study, providing a "nanomaterial score" based on 10 physicochemical parameters deemed most important (Table 3). This approach is encouraged to promote the notion that for studies conducted with NMs, the combination of a reliable study and sufficient NM characterization is of significantly greater value than

either of these alone. The authors anticipated that the use and evolution of this approach will assist with the design and interpretation of studies assessing NM toxicity. Indeed, other strategies have emerged, such as the Nanomaterials Registry initiative developed by the US National Institutes of Health based on minimal information about nanomaterials (MIAN) in order to be able to establish evaluation and similarity measures for data curated into the Registry (Ostraat et al, 2013). The MIAN are used to calculate a compliance-level numerical score that serves as a quality- and quantity-label of mainly the physicochemical characterization data performed for a specific NM, similarly as the Card & Magnuson method. In addition, ECHA recently listed NM-specific information requirements to support (quantitative) structure-activity relationship ((Q)SAR) modelling to allow for grouping and read-across (ECHA, 2017). The requirements largely overlap with the physicochemical properties listed by Card & Magnuson (2010). Further suggestions on how to evaluate quality of curated NM data were listed by Marchese Robinson et al. (2016) and include recommendations on terminology standardisation (i.e. a common ontology), specific (meta)data requirements, computational tools to support evaluation of completeness and quality, strategies for improving completeness and quality assessment, and the role of specific organizations and scientific communities in advancing the manner in which the completeness and quality of curated NM data are evaluated (Marchese Robinson et al, 2016). To date there is no definitive consensus regarding exactly how data quality should be defined in the nanoscience, or wider scientific, community.

Table 3. Ten parameters used to assess the completeness of NM physicochemical characterization in Card & Magnuson (2010). Each parameter contributes 1 point to the “nanomaterial score” in the method.

	Details (quoted from paper ¹)
1	agglomeration and/or aggregation
2	chemical composition
3	crystal structure/crystallinity
4	particle size/size distribution

5	purity*
6	shape
7	surface area
8	surface charge
9	surface chemistry (including composition and reactivity)
10	whether any characterization was conducted in the relevant experimental media

For ecotoxicity data, although availability of data has increased in recent years, there is an overarching issue of poor reliability in testing (Hjorth et al. 2017), partly as it is still debated to what degree standardised guideline testing is suitable for NMs (Hansen et al. 2017). Recently, Hartmann et al. (2017) proposed a framework to evaluate the regulatory reliability and relevance of ecotoxicity studies on NMs. The framework, referred to as NanoCRED, assesses reliability by a) the appropriateness of the study design for the purpose of NM testing, b) documentation provided on the study design, c) data on inherent NM properties and d) NM characterisation in the test system and during the test. The result is categorization in one of four categories of reliability based on the Klimisch system. For reliability, the assessment is the same as for chemicals (Moermond et al. 2016), however NanoCRED provides nano-specific guidance on the scoring. The open-access web-tool SCIRAP (Science in Risk Assessment and Policy, scirap.org) operationalizes the NanoCRED framework and allows for fast evaluation of relevance and reliability of ecotoxicity studies on nanomaterials.

In conclusion, relevance, reliability and completeness assessment and labelling should be part of a well-defined nanocuration workflow. Curated nanosafety data can be assumed to be sufficiently complete and of sufficient quality to serve its intended purpose of answering particular scientific or regulatory questions. Thus, the current deliverable outlines the approach taken in caLIBRAte Task 5.2 to develop a quality assessment method in light of recent advances in the field, as described above.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Inventory of previous quality assessment efforts

Information on previous initiatives for data quality assessment were collected in an inventory (Annex 1) to identify the different aspects and perceptions of the definition of quality. Partners of Task 5.2 contributed with knowledge on quality assessment efforts within their fields of expertise, including quality criteria previously developed for physicochemical characterization, toxicity, exposure and environmental fate.

2.2 Data requirements

Data requirements for the HRA and ERA models, selected in Tasks 2.2 and 3.2, were analysed in Tasks 5.1 and 7.1, and compulsory model parameters, i.e. the parameters that are required in an experimental dataset in order to be useful for model testing, were listed in D5.1. These parameters include both nanospecific and non-nanospecific parameters, the latter being parameters that are not retrieved from databases, but rather relate to the exposure scenario being assessed (e.g. river depth or room ventilation rate). In addition, data requirements for general quality assessment were also analysed in Task 5.1 and listed in D5.1, where they are referred to as minimal compulsory entries. These lists of data requirements were used here to develop a caLIBRAte strategy for assessment of relevance, reliability and completeness. Thus, the lists include: compulsory model input parameters (Annex 2), minimal compulsory entries for physicochemical characterization data of NM, here referred to as minimum information checklists for physicochemical characterization (Annex 3), and minimal compulsory entries for toxicity data, here referred to as minimum information checklists for toxicity data (including *in vivo*, *in vitro*, ecotoxicity, exposure and environmental fate data; Annex 4). The checklists on exposure and environmental fate criteria are strongly related to developments in WP6, which will continue the work on quality assessment of these types of data. Nevertheless, they have been included here to harmonize the handling and quality assessment strategies of diverse types of data.

Additional data requirements, based on ECHA's NM-specific information requirements for grouping and (Q)SAR, as well as the needs of the caLIBRAte System of Systems (SoS) framework and the NanoReg2 Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) were also assessed in Task 5.1 (e.g. source of data, information on methodology/SOPs etc). Since the caLIBRAte SoS and NanoReg2 SIA were still in early stages of development at that time point such requirements had not been defined yet. This information will be added to an updated version of D5.1 and subsequently inform the caLIBRAte quality assessment strategy. However, in a recent appendix (Appendix R.6-1) to the Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment, ECHA has listed some key physicochemical parameters to be considered for grouping and read-across of nanoforms, including the so called "What they are", "Where they go" and "What they do" parameters, as well as a few hazard-relevant parameters, which are also used for chemicals (ECHA, 2017). Thus, these parameters were included in Annex 2.

2.3 Linkage of data requirements to adequate physicochemical characterization and toxicological assays

Much of the nanosafety data originates from physicochemical characterization and toxicological assays, and since results from different assays should be interpreted differently, a further focus was put on the adequacy of the type of assays for addressing RA model requirements. Thus, the compulsory model input parameters (Annex 2) were further linked to assays deemed adequate for retrieving the necessary data. The assessment of adequate assays was based on partner expertise and on review of the existing data based on the database survey summarized in D5.1. An additional focus was put on listing next generation assays, such as omics and high-throughput screening (HTS), since these may be of importance for further refinement of the RA models in Tasks 2.4 and 3.4. Adequate assays were listed next to each parameter required for the RA models and serve as guidance during the quality assessment strategy in caLIBRAte, particularly in relation to reliability assessment. The strategy can later be refined to include assessment and potential labelling of assay adequacy, particularly upon publication of results from the GUIDEnano project, which has developed additional requirements for reliability assessment, relating to the assays used.

2.4 Linkage of data requirements and adequate assays to ontology

The EU FP7 project eNanoMapper has developed an automated Semantic Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) method that is useful for testing the completeness of data (eNanoMapper deliverable D5.6). The method can be used to automatically score and label datasets according to their level of relevance, reliability and completeness. However, the method is entirely dependent on the use of a well-developed ontology. Thus, the work in Task 5.2 included mapping of RA model parameters, minimum information checklists and relevant assays to IDs in the eNanoMapper ontology through the Bioportal repository interface (<http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ENM>).

RA model parameters (Annex 2) were linked to ontology IDs under the parent term “information content entity” (IAO_0000030) and refer to the specific ontology ID that should be used when addressing the parameter, i.e. when gathering data relevant to the parameter or when referring to the parameter in other contexts. Information content entity is defined as “*A generically dependent continuant that is about some thing*”. Similarly, physicochemical parameters (Annex 3) were linked to ontology IDs under the parent term “quality” (BFO:0000019), which is defined as “*a quality is a specifically dependent continuant that, in contrast to roles and dispositions, does not require any further process in order to be realized*”. The toxicity-related parameters (Annex 4) were linked to ontology IDs under which relevant child terms useful for describing the diverse toxicity endpoints, can be found or could be included in further refinements of the ontology itself. For example, the term cell line (EFO_0000322) contains various child terms describing a wide variety of cell lines, which can be used to describe the culture type under the minimum information checklist for *in vitro* data. Furthermore, assays deemed adequate for data retrieval to answer specific model input parameters, were linked to ontology IDs under the parent term “assay” (OBI_0000070), which is a child term to “process” (BFO_0000015).

The caLIBRAte database will include the use of the eNanoMapper ontology (described in D5.2) and thus later allows for implementation of the eNanoMapper automated SPARQL query language-based quality/completeness testing method.

Finally, an analysis of the ontology coverage of the model parameters, physicochemical characterization/toxicity information checklists and assays was performed to identify areas in the ontology, which are in need of development.

2.5 Development of a quality assessment and labelling method

An evaluation of the previous initiatives was performed and a caLIBRAte-specific quality assessment method was developed based on the most relevant previous initiatives. Elements from the most commonly used and widely accepted methods were adopted and integrated to be suitable for the specific purpose of the caLIBRAte project, taking into account the recent advances and ongoing discussions within the field.

To be able to assign quality labels to data in the caLIBRAte database, a labelling method was developed in parallel, largely based on previous initiatives (Annex 1), as well as the compulsory model input parameters, and the minimum information checklists on physicochemical characterization and toxicity data.

3. Results

3.1 Evaluation of previous quality assessment efforts

Eleven different approaches were listed, ranging from general toxicity to nano-specific needs, such as the Klimisch scoring system and the nano-refined version by Card & Magnuson (2010), as well as

from initiatives within EU and national projects, such as GUIDEnano and the DaNa Literature Criteria Checklist, to community-wide efforts, such as the Nanomaterial Registry MIAN-based numerical scoring method. Documents relating to the previous initiatives have been uploaded in [CIRCABC](#) (Annex 1).

The inventory includes a recent review discussing previous efforts, including many of the other initiatives listed, which summarizes the current situation on completeness and quality assessment of NM data and addresses the question of “how to evaluate the degree to which curated NM data are ‘sufficiently complete’ and of ‘acceptable quality’ (Marchese Robinson et al, 2016). The authors also define the terms data completeness and data quality (see the Introduction) and recommend that the definitions be agreed upon and formally established *via* e.g. the International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) or some other standardisation body. Further, the authors of the review suggest how to most appropriately score the degree of completeness and quality for a given NM data collection. Nine methods were discussed in the review, including Hristozov et al. 2012; DaNa “Literature Criteria Checklist”; Lubinski et al. 2013; Simkó et al., 2015; Nanotechnology Knowledge Infrastructure (NKI) Signature Initiative; Nanomaterial Registry; MOD-ENP-TOX and ModNanoTox; MODern (FP7 project); and the ToxRTool. In addition the inventory also included the following six quality assessment approaches: NANoREG, Card & Magnusson et al. 2010, the Dutch project NanoNextNL, EFSA quality criteria for the risk assessment of BPA, GUIDEnano quality approach, and the DTU concept for evaluation of ecotoxicological data for NMs (NanoCRED).

It is worth noting that many of the methods build on each other. For example, the GUIDEnano approach is based on further developments of the Card & Magnusson et al. (2010) approach, which is largely based on a nano-specific extension of the ToxRTool. Similarly, the NanoCRED approach for quality assessment of ecotoxicological data implements the ToxRTool strategy. A brief summary of the evaluation of the methodologies and their applicability to the caLIBRAte project is given in Table 4. The result of the evaluations was used as a basis and a starting point for the development of a quality labelling strategy for caLIBRAte.

Table 4. Evaluation of previous quality assessment initiatives.

Method	Short description	Applicability for Calibrate
Hristozov et al., 2012	Reliability of toxicity data in NM databases based purely upon the availability of basic provenance metadata: data were considered “unusable”, or “unreliable”, where a result from a study is not accompanied by a “properly cited reference”.	This is a simple assessment system, caLIBRAte needs a more sophisticated system for quality assessment. Possibly applicable for data completeness assessment.
DaNa “Literature Criteria Checklist”	To assess the quality of a given published study concerning a given NM for the purpose of preventing low quality scientific findings from being integrated within the DaNa knowledge base.	The Literature Criteria Checklist is valuable for the evaluation of publications. The criteria mentioned in the checklist can be used within caLIBRAte. However, there is no scoring system described related to the checklist.
Lubinski et al., 2013	<p>Framework for collecting and evaluating existing data based on both <i>the quality evaluation</i> and the usefulness for developing computational models.</p> <p>An extension of the Klimisch framework for evaluating the reliability of nanotoxicology, or nano-physicochemical, data which was considered, in part, to depend upon compliance of Good Laboratory Practice and standardised test protocols.</p> <p><i>Physicochemical characterization.</i> Size, shape, crystalline form, surface modification.</p> <p><i>Description of the experiment.</i> standard protocols (OECD guidance, US-EPA, etc.), completeness of the description, documentation.</p> <p><i>Performance:</i> According to GLPs Assignment of a qualitative score.</p>	<p>Possibly applicable, focus on evaluation of NM physicochemical and toxicological data for (Q)SAR assessment.</p> <p>Emphasis on the characterization of NM in each experiment and the existence of standard protocols. Scoring system is somewhat subjective. Difficult to have studies for NM under GLPs and standard guidelines.</p> <p>It has been evaluated with a high amount of data points (341) from 42 papers.</p>
Simkó et al., 2015	A range of criteria for evaluating <i>in vitro</i> studies, including clearly specified criteria for the statistical “quality of study”. It assigns a qualitative score.	Possibly applicable, the focus is on the evaluation of <i>in vitro</i> studies.
Nanotechnology Knowledge Infrastructure (NKI)	“Data Readiness Levels” scheme assigns any kind of data (i.e. not necessarily generated for NMs) to one of seven, ranked categories denoting their “quality and	Possibly applicable, focus on ranking.

Signature Initiative	maturity”.	
Nanomaterial Registry	<p>MIAN criteria developed by the Registry team, and specific to physicochemical characterization (PCC) and studies on biological and environmental interactions of NMs.</p> <p>A compliance level (CL) feature has been defined and provides a metric on the quality and quantity of characterization for each NM entry. Initial weighting factors have been assigned to each PCC (high weight: composition, size, surface chemistry/low weight: aggregation/agglomeration and purity)</p>	<p>Focus on scoring system so it could be useful to establish a scoring system for caLIBRAte. It is focused on main aspects such as physicochemical, toxicological and environmental studies but it has only been in use for physicochemical parameters. In a future curated data for biological and environmental studies will be introduced. No access to the weighting system is provided.</p>
MOD-ENP-TOX and ModNanoTox	Curation of NM data resources, also developed quality scoring schemes which assign numeric scores.	Possibly applicable, focus on scoring system.
MODern (FP7 project)	Development of ISA-TAB-Nano which comprises four spreadsheets based file formats (Investigation, Study, Assay and Material) for representing and integrating various types of NM data. This format integrates NM descriptions, assay data (metadata and endpoint measurements) and protocol information.	It gives a standard approach to representing NM data enabling sharing of NM information and to make cross-material comparisons. It does not seem to give any quality system but it may be a good way for reporting data and for studying the data completeness.
NANoREG	<p>Implementation of a series of general protocols and working methodologies to guarantee data quality.</p> <p>The general methodologies were collected under the NANoREG Guidance Document.</p> <p>The methodologies were based on physicochemical properties and divided into four categories; mandatory (M), optional (O), not applicable (NA) and applicability not confirmed (X).</p> <p>Development of nano-specific SOPs for <i>in vitro</i>, <i>in vivo</i> and ecotox imposed on all experiments. More than one lab performing each experiment.</p>	<p>The NANoREG project implements a compulsory physicochemical characterization prior, during and after experimentation to ensure experimental reproducibility and data interpretation.</p> <p>The systematic working approach implemented under the NANoREG project could set the basis for the quality data assessment required in caLIBRAte.</p>
ToxRTool	Evaluation of the reliability of toxicological data through a software developed by ECVAM in which	It covers <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> toxicology tests. It is quantitative, easy to use and

	<p>specific criteria are assigned to <i>in vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> experiments and a scoring system is given for each criteria.</p> <p>The tool comprises a list of 21 criteria for <i>in vivo</i> studies and 18 criteria for <i>in vitro</i> studies grouped into 5 groups respectively: test substance identification, test system characterisation, study design description, study results documentation and plausibility of study design and results. To each criteria met a 1 is assigned and if it is not met a 0.</p>	<p>readily available. The questions are included in a general and somewhat subjective way (i.e. is all information on the nature and/or physicochemical properties of the test item given, which you deem indispensable for judging the data?). It could be of value to caLIBRAte, but some refinement of the questions should be made. It does not cover physicochemical data quality. Inputs from NANoREG guidance compulsory parameters may be used to fill some gaps in this model.</p>
<p>Card & Magnuson et al 2010</p>	<p>A 2-step method to assess the quality of nanotoxicity studies is described. It involves the evaluation of the reliability of a given study and the adequacy of the characterization of the physicochemical parameters of the NMs in the study.</p> <p>1st step. Use of the ToxRTool to rank the reliability (Study (S) score)</p> <p>2nd step. Assess the completeness of physicochemical characterization (Nanomaterial (N) score)</p> <p>This approach promotes the notion that for studies conducted with NMs, the combination of a reliable study and sufficient NM characterization is of significantly greater value than either of these alone.</p>	<p>The applicability is to <i>in vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> toxicology studies. Both data completeness and reliability of the study are addressed and a scoring system is proposed. A list of physicochemical parameters is given as essential for NM. It seems highly relevant and useful for caLIBRAte.</p> <p>However, the ToxRTool (the basis of this proposed method) is not validated to evaluate ecotoxicity studies.</p>
<p>Dutch project NanoNextNL</p>	<p>Description of criteria for the evaluation and labeling of data quality on the NM (physicochemical properties and toxicity) to be inserted into the Data Support System (DSS).</p> <p>In addition, the criteria need to be applied by the user of the DSS to evaluate the quality of the data for which an output of the DSS is desired (physicochemical data of newly developed materials). This is to inform the user of the DSS on the quality of the dataset which is</p>	<p>This quality assessment system looks useful for caLIBRAte, since this system is specifically developed for data quality assessment of NMs. In addition, a labelling method was described to include the data quality assessment in a database. A disadvantage for using this method within caLIBRAte is that it is not currently in use and this system has only</p>

	used and consequently on the reliability of the output.	been tested in 3 cases.
EFSA quality criteria for the risk assessment of BPA	The focus of EFSA is on risk assessment. It is based on implementation of assessment processes characterised by e.g. upfront development of protocols; clear rules to collect, validate, analyse and integrate evidence; and rigorous methods for documenting processes and results	It does not seem useful for caLIBRAte as the description of a data quality assessment method is lacking. EFSA has focused mainly on principles and processes for dealing with data and evidence in scientific assessments.
GUIDEnano quality approach	Adaptation and refinement of the publication of Card and Magnuson (2010) Modification of the questions of the ToxRTool to avoid expert judgement. Development of a similar approach for ecotoxicity studies Establishment of a list of the physicochemical properties that should be reported for the NM and its life cycle products in an (eco)toxicity study and of the criteria to score them. Definition of the criteria to establish the quality categories for the K-S score (according to Card & Magnuson - see above).	This system seems highly relevant and useful for caLIBRAte. Both, data completeness and reliability are addressed and a scoring system is proposed. Moreover, GUIDEnano modified the 2-step approach in order to assess also ecotoxicological studies. The other adaptations made seem needed for the GUIDEnano Tool, but not necessarily for caLIBRAte. The method is not publically available at the time of writing (June 2017).
The DTU concept for evaluation of ecotoxicological data for NMs (NanoCRED)	A scoring system for assessing the regulatory adequacy of ecotoxicological studies of NMs for Predicted No-Effect Concentration (PNEC) estimation. It assesses: <i>Reliability</i> according to a list of 21 criteria focusing on the characterisation and exposure of the NM. <i>Relevance</i> according to a list of 13 criteria. Each criterion is assessed on a scale from 0-3 and assigned a weight from 1-3.	This quality method is based on the Klimisch categories and the ToxRTool. The described quality scoring system seems relevant for the evaluation of ecotoxicological studies within caLIBRAte.

3.2 The caLIBRAte quality assessment method

Based on the definitions of quality in Klimisch et al. (1997) and the review by Marchese Robinson et

al. (2016; Table 1) the partners of Task 5.2 decided that data relevance, reliability and completeness should be assessed separately in caLIBRAte. Data relevance is related to a specific dataset's ability to be fit-for-purpose, i.e. fulfill the needs of a specific requirement, which in the caLIBRAte project can be related to the requirements of the RA models. Data quality is related to the reliability (i.e. the level of trustworthiness, reproducibility, repeatability, uncertainty and error) of a dataset and is associated with the adequacy of the assay used, adequate reporting of metadata and the use of SOPs. Finally, data completeness is related to the adequate assessment of key physicochemical parameters of NMs.

Based on the above, a 3-step strategy was established to assess data relevance, reliability and completeness (Figure 2). The first step, relevance, is caLIBRAte-specific and is based on the compulsory model input parameters listed for each selected RA model (HRA and ERA models), as well as ECHA's NM-specific information requirements for grouping and (Q)SARs (ECHA, 2017). It is set as the first step in the strategy, since the gathering of data in Task 5.2 should start from data that is as relevant as possible to performance testing of the models (WP7). The next two steps address quality on a more general level and are largely based on the previous initiative by Card & Magnuson (Nr 11 in the Inventory – Annex 1). The second step, reliability, is based on the ToxRTTool, which applies Klimisch scores and currently is developed to assess *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies. The method has also been implemented in GUIDEnano, which will provide support for the refinement of the method within caLIBRAte, when publically available (expected within the next few months). In addition, initial development towards assessment of the adequacy of the assay used to generate the data was included in this step and will be further refined based on results from GUIDEnano, which has addressed the issue. For ecotoxicity data, the SCIRAP web-tool will perform the same assessment based on the NanoCRED framework. The third and final step, completeness, is focused on assessing whether adequate physicochemical characterization has been performed. The minimum information checklist for physicochemical characterization (Annex 3) were used to refine the original list of 10

parameters as defined by Card & Magnuson (2010). Furthermore, the step has also been implemented in the GUIDEnano strategy and will provide support for later refinement of the method within caLIBRAte.

The 3-step method is flexible and can later be applied in a different order, based on the refinement of the risk assessment models in WP2 and WP3, which may bring up the need for new types of data or require the assessment of quality before relevance.

Figure 2. The caLIBRAte strategy for assessing data relevance, reliability and completeness

3.2.1 Relevance

The relevance is assessed according to the compulsory model input parameters (Annex 2). These parameters were assessed and listed in Task 5.1/D5.1, and grouped into distinct categories according to NM properties, interaction, matrix, system dimensions and conditions, which allowed for separation between nano and non-nano parameters (see D5.1 for detailed descriptions on the matter). For

example, the HRA model NanoSafer CB requires 25 parameters of which 10 are nano-specific, 9 are nano-specific or based on the nearest analogue bulk material, and 6 are non-nanospecific system dimension/condition-based parameters. LICARA nanoSCAN requires 24 parameters, of which 13 are nano-specific. LICARA nanoSCAN includes (parts of) the other HRA models StoffenManager Nano for occupational risk assessment, and parameters from the Precautionary Matrix for consumer (and environmental) risk assessment. For the Precautionary Matrix 9 of 10 parameters are nano-specific. The GUIDEnano tool requires the most parameters of all HRA models, namely 18 nano-specific parameters out of a total of 34 parameters. For the ERA models, both SB4N and MendNano require 25 parameters of which 17 are nano-specific. NanoQSAR requires only 1 nano-specific parameter and SSWD requires 10 nano-specific parameters. Finally, ECHA's NM-specific information requirements for grouping and (Q)SARs include 26 parameters, of which 18 overlap with the RA model parameters.

Thus, for example, data relevant for the RA tool NanoSafer CB are assessed as to whether results for product type, the NM properties density, particle size (average size, size-range) and size distribution, dustiness, surface coating, particle shape and surface area exist. In addition, results for the interaction parameters solubility (in water) and substance release rate (dustiness or mass emission rate) are needed. Finally, results for several hazard characterization parameters, including carcinogenicity and allergy/sensitization, as well as system dimension/exposure condition parameters are needed, but these do not necessarily need to be obtained from studies on the specific NM at hand, but can be retrieved from studies on the nearest analogue bulk material based on chemical and structural identity. Currently, up to 25 parameters are required to use the NanoSafer CB tool and the relevance of the available data is assessed according to how well it fulfills that requirement.

The results from this step will also inform Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 on relevant data gaps and needs to fill them.

3.2.2 Reliability

Reliability, based on the Klimisch scoring system, initially implements the original ToxRTool approach. The approach will later be refined based on the minimum information checklists for each of the 5 types of data listed in Annex 4. The minimum information checklists for *in vitro* and *in vivo* data cover the “red criteria” in the ToxRTool and thus correspond well to the current criteria of the tool. Nevertheless, a few of the minimum information checklist criteria are not covered by the ToxRTool and warrant further refinement. However, since GUIDEnano has worked on refinement of the criteria in the tool, the partners of Task 5.2 decided not to duplicate work and instead wait for the information to become publically available, which is expected to be obtained within the current year (2017).

For example, for ecotoxicity data, the reliability scoring in NanoCRED developed by Hartmann et al. (2017) is directly tailed to assess NMs. Further refinement of the method includes implementation of the approach used within the GUIDEnano project, which further developed the questions in the tool and implemented novel criteria for ecotoxicological data using the same approach. In addition, GUIDEnano also worked towards refinement of methods for assessing reliability of physicochemical characterization and exposure (including release/emission) data, which will be implemented in caLIBRAte. The latter will, however, be assessed further in WP6, which is focused on evaluation and re-analysis of life-cycle data for demonstration of the caLIBRAte risk governance framework.

In addition, the adequacy of the assay(s) used to gather the data were assessed. In Annex 2, assays used within the databases surveyed for and listed in D5.1 were linked with the compulsory model input parameters and can in future refinement of the method be weighed according to their adequacy (initially all types of assays will be considered adequate). Based on experience from the pharma industry, regulatory assays should have the maximum adequacy even if it regards an *in vitro* assay. A proposed approach for assessing the adequacy will then be:

Regulatory assays (+GLP) > validated assays + GLP > validated assays > non-validated assays

Validated assays have gone through comprehensive experiments that evaluate and document the quantitative performance of an assay, including sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, precision, detection limit, range and limits of quantitation. Full assay validation includes inter-assay and inter-laboratory assessment of assay repeatability and robustness.

For all non-regulatory assays the adequacy can be defined according to the classical approach in hazard assessment, in the following way:

Human biomonitoring studies > in vivo mammalian studies > (in vivo non-mammalian studies = in vitro mammalian studies) > in vitro non-mammalian studies > acellular studies

Adequate assays were largely identified based on assays used in previous projects as described in the results of the database survey performed together with the Nanosafety Cluster in caLIBRAte Task 5.1 and documented in D5.1. For example, adequate assays for mutagenicity could be represented by those accepted by regulatory bodies, such as the OECD, including in vitro mammalian cell gene mutation assays (OECD 476, 490), the micronucleus assay (OECD 487) and the chromosomal aberrations in vitro assay (OECD 473). Less adequate, but still useful assays include the comet assay (commercial kit for in vivo or in vitro), for which only a prevalidation study is available. The Ames test, though accepted by the OECD, is not adequate to NM according to recent studies, since NMs do not seem to cross the bacterial wall and, in addition, some NMs have anti-bacterial properties (Doak et al. 2012). For next generation assays, transcriptomics, proteomics, miRNA expression profiling, metabolomics, AOP-based assays, protein corona profiling, high-content imaging/analysis data and HTS data were considered adequate and useful for future RA model refinement work planned in Tasks 2.4 and 3.4.

3.2.3 Completeness

Based on step 2 in the Card & Magnuson method, completeness is assessed according to the minimum information checklist for physicochemical characterization (Annex 3). The list used in

caLIBRAte is similar to the original list of physicochemical characterization criteria in Card & Magnuson (2010), except for the addition of stability (solubility, dissolution rate) and the distinction of size (size-range) and size distribution into two separate criteria. Furthermore, the list in Annex 3 excludes a specific criteria for whether any characterization was performed in relevant experimental media (refer to Table 3), since this point is included under the reliability assessment in step 2 of the caLIBRAte method, because it is highly related to the assay used and its adequacy.

The minimum information checklist for physicochemical parameters may be subject to refinement, as knowledge about key overarching properties increases (Marchese Robinson et al. 2016). Thus, within caLIBRAte a version history of different lists will be kept, the current version in Annex 3, referred to as caLIBRAte v1.

Considering the NM-specific recommendations by ECHA on the endpoints needed for (Q)SAR modelling and grouping (ECHA, 2017), the checklist for physicochemical characterization (Annex 3) covers most of the recommended endpoints, including six nanoform identity endpoints (i.e. “What they are”) and five behavioral endpoints (i.e. “Where they go”). One of the behavioral endpoints, namely hydrophobicity, can be derived from knowledge on the surface chemistry, which is included in the list. The two reactivity endpoints (“What they do”), i.e. surface- and photoreactivity are not covered in the checklist, but can also potentially be derived from the previous parameters, such as surface chemistry and charge.

3.3 Mapping ontology terms to parameters and assays

To enable future automated quality assessment, ontology terms corresponding to the data requirements (both compulsory model input parameters and minimum information checklists) were mapped from the eNanoMapper ontology. In addition, ontology terms corresponding to the adequate

assays were listed. Terms associated with the sub-categories “information content entity” (for model parameters), “process” (for assays) and “quality” (for quality assessment criteria were prioritized and otherwise all suitable terms were listed (Annexes 2-4).

For the human RA (HRA) model parameters 12/16 NM property parameters, 5/7 interaction parameters, 11/15 matrix (toxicity) parameters, 0/2 system dimensions parameters, and 1/19 conditions parameters were identified in the ontology. In total 29/57 (51%) HRA model parameters were covered by the ontology. For the environmental RA (ERA) models 11/13 NM property parameters, 2/10 interaction parameters, 2/5 matrix parameters 0/3 system dimension parameters, and 2/5 conditions parameters were identified in the ontology. In total 17/36 (47%) ERA model parameters were covered by the ontology. For the ECHA-based information requirements 18/26 parameters were covered by ontology IDs.

For the minimum information checklists for physicochemical characterization (Annex 3) all 11 criteria (100%) could be identified in the ontology. Eighteen of a total of 31 (58%) relevant assays for measuring physicochemical parameters corresponded to ontology terms. For *in vivo* experiments (Annex 4), 8/17 (47%) criteria corresponded to ontology terms. Similarly, for *in vitro* experiments (Annex 4), 8/16 (50%) criteria could be annotated with ontology terms. For ecotoxicity data, 4/14 (29%) criteria were represented in the ontology. For *in vivo*, *in vitro* and ecotoxicological experiments, two criteria were not relevant for ontology annotation as they refer to the number of subjects/replicates and treatment groups. For exposure data, 6/20 (30%) criteria, and for environmental fate data, 6/10 (60%) criteria were represented by ontology terms.

3.4 Assessment and scoring methodology

Based on the caLIBRAte quality assessment strategy data/datasets will obtain 3 scores derived from the 3 steps of relevance, reliability and completeness.

Step 1: Assessment of Relevance

The scoring for relevance is based on the fulfillment of the compulsory model input parameters and is thus model-specific, ranging from a relevance (R) score of R0 (lowest relevance) to Rx (highest relevance), where x is equal to the total number of parameters required for a specific model. To assess the relevance the following steps are required:

- a. The number of parameters for each selected tool is listed
- b. A study is relevant for caLIBRAte if the required parameters per tool are described
- c. Result of the assessment of relevance is the number of parameters available per tool

Example

Twenty-five parameters are required for the NanoSafer tool. Each parameter reported contributes for 1 point to the total score of 23. If 15 parameters are reported, a study score of R15 can be assigned for the Nanosafer tool.

Step 2: Assessment of Study Reliability

The second step uses the ToxRTTool, a software-based tool that was designed, tested, and released for public use by the European Centre for the Validation of Alternative Methods (ECVAM). It is freely available for noncommercial use at the ECVAM Web site (<http://ecvam.jrc.it/>; “Publications” section). This tool is based on the categorization system for toxicological and ecotoxicological data that was proposed by Klimisch et al. (1997). There are 2 versions of the tool, one for evaluating *in vivo* studies and the other for evaluating *in vitro* studies. The ToxRTTool evaluates the reliability of any *in vivo* or *in vitro* human toxicity study using generic questions about: 1) Test substance identification; 2) Test system characterization; 3) Study design description; 4) Study results documentation and 5) Plausibility design and results. For the *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies 21 or 18 questions, respectively, have to be answered in terms of 1 (yes) or 0 (no). From these questions some are identified as “red questions” (see Table 5). The sum of the positive questions will determine the assignment of the study

to Klimisch categories of K1 (reliable without restrictions), K2 (reliable with restrictions), K3 (unreliable), or K4 (not assignable due to insufficient experimental details) according to the categories established by Klimisch et al. (1997). Additionally if a study does not answer one of the “red questions”, the study is automatically placed in K3, regardless of the overall score that the study receives. Klimisch category 4 (K4) is not calculated by the ToxRtool but rather it is assigned by the reviewer’s assessment of the study or report under evaluation. This categorization is recognized and used by regulators from different agencies (OECD, US EPA, ECHA, GHS, etc.), by the academia and it can be applied to any study to be classified by its reliability.

Further refinement of the questions, particularly with regard to ecotoxicity and physicochemical characterization data, is expected within the next few months based on results from the GUIDEnano project, and will be implemented in the caLIBRAte strategy, as well as described in an addendum to the current deliverable (D5.3) describing the results of a case study during the next year of the project.

Table 5. Information required for a study to be assigned to Klimisch category 1 or 2^a.

Criteria Number ^b	Question
In vivo studies	
1.	Was the test substance identified?
5.	Is the species given?
10.	Is the administration route given?
11.	Are doses administered or concentrations in application media given?
12.	Are frequency and duration of exposure as well as time points of observations explained?
13.	Were negative (where required) and positive controls (where required) included (give point also, when absent but not required, see explanations for study types, and their respective requirements on controls)?
14.	Is the number of animals (in case of experimental human studies: number of test persons) per group given?
20.	Is the study design chosen appropriate for obtaining the substance-specific data aimed at (see explanations for details)?
In vitro studies	
1.	Was the test substance identified?
9.	Are doses administered or concentrations in application media given?
10.	Are frequency and duration of exposure as well as time points of observations explained?
11.	Were negative controls included (give also point, if not necessary, see explanations)?
12.	Were positive controls included (give also point, if not necessary, see explanations)?
17.	Is the study design chosen appropriate for obtaining the substance-specific data aimed at (see explanations for details)?

^a Also described as “red criteria.”

^b Refers to the criteria number in the ToxRTool spreadsheets for in vivo and in vitro studies (available for download at <http://ecvam.jrc.it/>; “Publications” section).

Step 3: Assessment of Nanomaterial Characterization

The third step involves determining the completeness of assessing the physicochemical properties of the NM(s) that is/are being measured within a given study as well as the adequacy of the reporting of the methods used to measure these properties. Based on Card & Magnuson (2010) as well as other initiatives a list of 11 key physicochemical properties was established. An N score from N0 to N11 will be assigned based on the amount of parameters reported in a given study. Each parameter contributes 1 point toward the total score.

The K and N scores are combined into a “study quality score K-N” that will indicate the overall quality of the study. Only studies placed in K1 or K2 are recommended to be further assessed for their sufficiency in reporting physicochemical data. Using this approach, an “ideal” study would be one judged to be in Klimisch category 1 and N score of 11, providing a nano study score of K1-N11.

In conclusion, a study/dataset of highest quality would receive a score of Rx-K1-N11, x depending on the number of parameters required for the RA model at hand (Figure 3). At this moment, no specific threshold was set as to whether a data is accepted or not, since all data will be considered, starting with the ones receiving the highest scores. Quality of specific datasets may improve with the generation of new data in Task 5.4 based on the gap analysis. Later thresholds for high quality can be assigned.

Figure 3. A schematic depiction of the assessment of the overall relevance and quality of an NM toxicity study based on its derived score. The clear area represents the range of scores for which a study can be considered of high overall quality; conversely, the shaded area represents the region of low overall quality.

Future refinement of the labelling method may also include weighting of certain criteria. The ToxRTool currently considers certain criteria as “red criteria”, which need to be fulfilled to reach sufficient quality levels, regardless of the overall score. Further development may include weighting of nano-specific

criteria based on regulatory requirements (ECHA's recommendations listed in Annex 2) and/or the minimum information checklists (Annex 3 and 4). In addition, weighting factors could be assigned to the level of adequacy of specific assays according to the description above. In fact, relevant assays for mutagenicity have been assessed in the GUIDEnano project and a manuscript on the subject has recently been submitted providing a basis for further development of the method (Catalan et al. submitted). For completeness, key overarching physicochemical parameters could be weighted when knowledge on those increases (Lynch et al. 2014).

Quality labels on data/datasets can be uploaded to the caLIBRAte database on a dataset- (relevance/completeness) or data point-basis (reliability). The labelling strategies can be refined and communicated further through the communication platform established by the eNanoMapper database developers at IDEA Consult, i.e. the Phabricator platform (<https://phabricator.ideaconsult.net/>). The platform will be a key asset in the communication towards harmonized data management and quality assessment within caLIBRAte and eventually standardised strategies within the community as a whole. In addition, the use of standardised data storage templates, such as ISA-TAB-Nano and the ISA-TAB-Nano-based Excel-templates developed by NANoREG (cf Table 4) and further refined by eNanoMapper, will become key to the implementation of automatic quality assessment and scoring.

4. Discussion of results

The work leading to this deliverable was initiated by the collection of information on previous initiatives towards setting data quality criteria and labelling methodologies within the nanosafety field (Annex 1). A recent review on data completeness and quality of curated NM data (Marchese Robinson et al, 2016), listed among the previous initiatives, states the importance of data completeness, relevance and quality (i.e. reliability/reproducibility and adequacy) as separate issues. In addition, commonly used quality assessment strategies, such as the Klimisch scoring-based ToxRTool, which assesses reliability of toxicity studies, and nano-specific refinements were reviewed (Schneider et al. 2009; Card

& Magnuson 2010). Based on this information, partners within the task decided that caLIBRAte, which is gathering data based on a minimum set of data requirements for a particular purpose i.e. to fulfill the needs of the RA models (chosen in Task 2.2 and 3.2), should focus initially on data relevance. Quality of the data gathered for that specific purpose was considered equally important and, a 3-step strategy was established, where data is initially, in a first step, assessed for *relevance* towards the data requirements by the RA models considered within caLIBRAte, and in a second and third step assessed for *reliability* of the data, and *completeness* of NM physicochemical characterization.

The relevance of data is assessed on the basis of whether the compulsory parameters, needed for the RA models to give relevant output, have been measured. Next, the reliability of data will initially be assessed based on the original ToxRTTool criteria. Refinement of the criteria in the tool has been performed within the EU FP7 project GUIDEnano and will, when publically available within the next few months, be considered for refinement of the caLIBRAte strategy. In addition, minimum information checklists for physicochemical characterization and for toxicity data were developed within caLIBRAte Task 5.1 (Annex 3 and 4) and will be considered for the refinement of the ToxRTTool criteria. To the benefit of the future refinements, currently, the weighted “red criteria” of the ToxRTTool are covered by the minimum information checklists developed in caLIBRAte, warranting harmonised use of the tool before and after refinement of the criteria. Finally, the completeness of data will be assessed based on whether the NM tested has been characterized adequately and confers to a list of 11 physicochemical characterization criteria. These criteria may also be refined later based on novel findings and identification of overarching properties governing toxicity, and/or based on experience and publications in other projects (Lynch et al. 2014). For example, the use of next generation data such as that obtained from omics assays may guide the refinement of the quality assessment method towards new types of criteria. Omics data are increasingly being applied in risk assessment strategies and warrant a decrease in uncertainty levels if used appropriately and in relation to e.g. the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) concept (Grafström et al. 2015). In fact, *in vitro* methods-derived transcriptomics data was recently shown to be widely predictive of *in vivo* outcome in liver (Kohonen et al. 2017). Quality assessment of omics data per se is currently well defined, while that of the associated NM characterization and experimental design could follow in the same lines as the strategy

described here (Powers et al. 2015; Sansone et al. 2012).

The data/datasets assessed by the caLIBRAte quality assessment method will be marked with 3 scores according to the 3 steps described above. The relevance will be measured as an R-score according to the number of parameters relevant to the specific tool being assessed. The reliability will be measured as a K-score (as in Klimisch) according to the compliance with the ToxRTool criteria. The completeness will be measured as an N-score according to the fulfillment of the 11 physicochemical characterization criteria. The proposed quality approach will be evaluated, tested and validated in the next year of the project, and the results of this validation will be presented in an addendum of D5.3.

It may be noted that although some of the previous initiatives focus on the quality aspects of physicochemical characterization data (e.g. Lubinski et al, the Nanomaterial Registry and Card & Magnuson), reliability assessment and assessment of the adequacy of the assays used has not been described extensively. The challenges related to the quality assessment of physicochemical characterization data was discussed by Marchese Robinson et al. (2016), who state that a definitive list of required parameters can currently not be established. This is largely due to e.g. various issues regarding the interrelatedness and the context dependency of the physicochemical properties, e.g. time dependent changes (i.e. ageing). The main recommendation by the authors is that for the time being, documentation and reporting of metadata is of extreme importance to later be able to estimate the usefulness of the data. For this reason, the quality assessment of physicochemical characterization data will still be subject to development and within the project we will refer to caLIBRAte-specific versions of e.g. minimum information checklists (Annex 3 being caLIBRAte v1).

The eNanoMapper automated quality and completeness labelling method (described in the results section) is entirely dependent on the use of the ontology when storing data (eNanoMapper D5.6). Thus, the parameters and criteria used to assess quality, as well as the assays listed as adequate for obtaining specific data, were mapped to eNanoMapper ontology terms. The mapping exercise demonstrated that physicochemical and human toxicity parameters, criteria and assays were fairly well covered (58%-100%). Environmental fate parameters were also covered to about 60%. However,

ecotoxicity and exposure-related parameters and assays did not show the same level of coverage (around 30%), indicating areas of development for the ontology. Furthermore, refinement of specific ontology IDs, parent terms and addition of child terms within all areas mentioned above, is recommended and can be based on the findings in this deliverable.

In conclusion, curated high quality data is key to successful development of e.g. (Q)SAR methods and other types of toxicity (or fate) predictive models, which eventually allow for grouping and read-across. Such methods and models are useful components of next generation state-of-the-art RA frameworks. For this reason, the RA models to be assessed, calibrated and refined in caLIBRAte WP2 and 3 depend on high quality data. The current deliverable outlines the approach that will be taken to assess the quality of data and datasets available from previous projects and generated within caLIBRAte. The deliverable sets the basis for a well-defined curation workflow and guides the data gathering in Task 5.2 during the remainder of the project. In addition, the deliverable will, together with the gap analysis (Task 5.3), serve as a guide for the generation of data in Task 5.4, with regard to the choice of adequate assays and the gathering of metadata necessary to increase the relevance, reliability and completeness of the data. Finally, implementation of the experience and knowledge gathered during the assessment of quality will be valuable for further development of the data management strategy taken within caLIBRAte (e.g. through the Phabricator communication platform, see Results). Eventually, well developed curation workflows and data management procedures will allow data producers to easily upload their data, which is subject to a quality check before submission, similarly as within the bioinformatics community (Sansone et al. 2012).

5. Conclusions and relevance for other caLIBRAte tasks

Within WP5, the current deliverable is of relevance for the continued work within Task 5.2 with regard to data gathering. The quality assessment strategy will be tested initially on selected use cases and later applied to further data gathered within the project. The deliverable is relevant for the generation of new data in Task 5.4 according to the most adequate assays and for guidance on the collection of metadata to increase the quality of newly generated data.

Within WP2 and WP3, Tasks 2.4 and 3.4 (Evaluation of the added value of innovative methods to reduce uncertainty in the RA models) benefit from the deliverable, which guides the quality assessment of next generation data such as omics and HTS, enabling use of the highest quality data for potential refinement of the RA models.

Within WP6, the deliverable will provide a basis for the further development of quality assessment method for exposure and environmental fate data. The quality assessment of these data types has been found to be strongly related to the tasks in WP6, particularly the gap analysis to identify emerging knowledge gaps and missing data from case studies in Task 6.2.

Within WP7, the deliverable is of direct relevance for the performance testing of the RA models. Only the highest quality datasets will be chosen in WP7 to test and calibrate the RA models.

As an additional point can be mentioned that the deliverable can be expected to be relevant for further development of the ontology, based on the parameters and assays that could not be linked with ontology IDs here. The ontology forms the basis for automated quality assessment and assists future collection of data in curated format. caLIBRAte does not include tasks on ontology development, however, providing information for future projects engaging in such tasks can be considered an overarching aim of all work performed in caLIBRAte.

6. Expected impact

Together with previous work in several EU projects, this deliverable sets the basis for further development and particularly for implementation of well-defined curation workflows. Experimentalist-driven curation of data into common databases, through use of harmonized/standardised ontology-implementing data templates, will allow for automated quality labelling and eventually efficient reuse of data for the development of novel risk predictive models (Powers et al. 2015).

7. Data management

The task and deliverable are part of WP5 and are directly related to the data management within the project.

8. Performance of partners

KI leads the work in Task 5.2 and has led the work underlying and the writing of the current deliverable. KI also mapped ontology terms to the quality criteria listed in Annexes 2-4. RIVM evaluated half of the previous initiatives for suitability within caLIBRAte and developed the first version of the quality assessment strategy used within caLIBRAte. GAIKER evaluated the other half of the previous initiatives and together with FIOH evaluated and assigned toxicological assays adequate for addressing compulsory model input parameters. FIOH has also contributed with extensive expertise on quality assessment based on experience in the GUIDEnano project. DTU has implemented quality assessment strategies relevant to ecotoxicity data, as well as reviewed the quality assessment-associated terminology used in the deliverable. TNO implemented expertise and information on the quality assessment of exposure data, listed compulsory model parameters for the GUIDEnano tool, and provided input on ontology mapping of quality criteria. LEITAT also contributed with expertise on the quality assessment of exposure and environmental fate data (which will be completed in WP6), and listed the GUIDEnano tool parameters in collaboration with TNO. R-Tech participated in task meetings in order to get the acquaintance with WP5 activities and to align the work in other work packages (e.g. WP1, WP4 and WP8), if deemed necessary.

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10. List of abbreviations

AOP	-	Adverse Outcome Pathway
BPA	-	Bisphenol A
CL	-	Compliance level
DSS	-	Data Support System
DTU	-	Technical University of Denmark
ECETOC TRA	-	European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals Targeted Risk Assessment
ECVAM	-	European Centre for the Validation of Alternative Methods
EFSA	-	European Food Safety Authority
NM	-	Manufactured nanomaterials
ERA	-	Environmental risk assessment
FIOH	-	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
GAIKER	-	Gaiker Technology Center, Spain
GLP	-	Good Laboratory Practice
HRA	-	Human risk assessment
KI	-	Karolinska Institute, Sweden
LEITAT	-	Leitat Technological Centre, Spain
MIAN	-	Minimal information about nanomaterials
NKI	-	Nanotechnology Knowledge Infrastructure
OECD	-	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCC	-	Physicochemical characterization
(Q)SAR	-	(Quantitative) structure-activity relationships
RA	-	Risk assessment
RDF	-	Resource Description Framework
REACH	-	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RIVM	-	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Netherlands
R-Tech	-	Steinbeis Advanced Risk Technologies, Germany
SCIRAP	-	Science in Risk Assessment and Policy
SOP	-	Standard operating procedure
SPARQL	-	Semantic Protocol and RDF Query Language

TNO	-	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
ToxRTool	-	Toxicological data Reliability Assessment Tool
UH	-	University of Helsinki, Finland
US-EPA	-	US Environmental Protection Agency

11. Annexes

Annex 1 - Inventory of previous initiatives on nanosafety data quality assessment

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caLIBRAte Task 5.2 will produce D5.3 - *A document on quality criteria for data*. We will collect information on previous initiatives in the area as well as experience and knowledge from caLIBRAte partners. The inventory will be used as a basis for developing quality criteria and a quality labelling method for the data gathered in caLIBRAte.

Partners are asked to add reports and documents on quality labelling to the list below. In addition, comments on **i)** what type of data, **ii)** which aspects of data quality are addressed, and **iii)** how the method could be useful for caLIBRAte are also welcome.

1. Nanomaterial Data Curation Initiative
 - i. **Highly relevant recent review:** [Marchese Robinson et al.](#) How should the completeness and quality of curated nanomaterial data be evaluated? *Nanoscale*, 2016, 8, 9919-9943
 - ii. Summarizes recent efforts (including several efforts listed below), discusses mature fields and gives recommendations
 - ✓Hristozov et al. Risk assessment of engineered nanomaterials: a review of available data and approaches from a regulatory perspective. *Nanotoxicology*, 2012, 6, 880–898.
 - ✓DaNa Literature Criteria Checklist (*see below*)
 - ✓Lubinski et al. (*see below*)
 - ✓Simkó et al. Pooling and Analysis of Published in Vitro Data: A Proof of Concept Study for the Grouping of Nanoparticles. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2015, 16, 26211–26236.

- ✓NSI: Nanotechnology Knowledge Infrastructure (NKI) Data Readiness Levels discussion draft, Nanotechnology Signature Initiative Nanotechnology Knowledge Infrastructure (NSI NKI), 2013.
 - ✓Nanomaterial Registry (*see below*)
 - ✓EU FP7 projects MOD-ENP-TOX and ModNanoTox (*see Marchese Robinson et al. 2016*)
 - ✓EU FP7 project MODern (MODERN Project Web Applications <http://modern-fp7.biocentit.cat/tools.html>; MODERN Project Homepage <http://modern-fp7.biocentit.cat/index.html>)
 - iii. Addresses both data completeness (possibly useful for gap analysis in Task 5.3) and data quality
- 2. the [Nanomaterial Registry database](#)
 - i. [Ostraat et al. 2013](#). The Nanomaterial Registry: facilitating the sharing and analysis of data in the diverse nanomaterial community. International Journal of Nanomedicine 8 (Suppl. D) (2013):7-13.
 - ii. Clear criteria that can be systematically used
 - iii. Minimal information about nanomaterials (MIAN) with regard to phys chem, biological interactions (human tox and ecotox) and environmental interactions (air, water, soil)
- 3. Quality criteria for the development of nano-QSARs
 - i. [Lubinski et al.](#) Evaluation criteria for the quality of published experimental data on nanomaterials and their usefulness for QSAR modelling. SAR QSAR Environ Res. (2013) 24(12):995-1008.
- 4. The German projects [DaNa](#) and DaNa^{2.0}
 - i. Established a Literature Criteria Checklist which includes the definition of mandatory and desirable assessment criteria in accordance with quality criteria that have been acknowledged worldwide within the scientific community
 - ii. This list is initially also being implemented in NanoReg2
 - iii. [DaNa criteria checklist](#)
- 5. [NANoREG guidance documents and SOPs](#)
 - i. Guidance Document on Minimum experimentation requirements. This document describes the minimum number of experiments to be carried out in order to guarantee cross-comparison among data generated in the project. It is based mainly on phys-chem data and microscope image.
 - ii. NANoREG toxicological analysis. Protocols were set up for viability, genotoxicity and immunotoxicity experimentation *in vitro*. As far as *in vivo* experimentation is concerned OECD guidelines or adaptations of such guidance were followed.
 - iii. The ENPRA dispersion protocol for NANoREG
 - iv. The NANOGENOTOX dispersion protocol for NANoREG
 - v. NanoREG SOP for TEM sample preparation CODA-CERVA
 - vi. Protocol for producing reproducible dispersions of manufactured nanomaterials in environmental exposure media

- vii. Preparation of aqueous dispersions of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) SOP
 - viii. SOP for probe-sonicator calibration of delivered acoustic power and de-agglomeration efficiency for in vitro and in vivo toxicological testing
 - ix. SOP for measurement of hydrodynamic Size-Distribution and Dispersion Stability by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)
 - x. etc.
6. Dutch project [NanoNextNL](#)
- i. Quality criteria for data on engineered nanomaterials for a Decision Support System
 - ii. Validation report: Evaluating the data quality labelling as proposed for the Decision Support System: three cases
7. [EFSA quality criteria](#) for the risk assessment of BPA
8. [GUIDEnano](#) quality approach (to be shared with caLIBRAte upon publication):
- i. Quality criteria for human and environmental toxicological data on nanomaterials.
 - ii. Evaluates the reliability and the completeness of data (e.g. the quality of toxicological data is checked both for the completeness of the reporting of the study (experimental set up etc) but also for adequate nanomaterial characterization)
 - iii. The quality criteria is part of the hazard data evaluation and is implemented on the web-based GUIDEnano Tool (a Tool for the Risk Assessment/ Risk Management Tool of engineered nanomaterials)
9. The [DTU \(et al.\)](#) concept for evaluation of ecotoxicological data for ENMs, includes:
- i. Reliability evaluation – documentation of experimental conditions and nanomaterial properties
 - ii. Relevance evaluation – applicability of data and test method
 - iii. Adequacy – combining reliability and relevance
10. [ToxRTool](#)
- i. Developed within the context of an ECVAM funded project to provide comprehensive criteria and guidance for evaluations of the inherent quality of toxicological data, thus making the decision process of assigning reliability categories more transparent and more harmonised
 - ii. [Schneider et al. 2009](#)
 - iii. Used in the GUIDEnano method
11. [Card & Magnuson et al 2010](#)
- i. “A 2-step method to assess the quality of nanotoxicity studies is described. The first step uses a publicly available tool to rank the reliability of the study based on adequacy of design and documentation of methods, materials, and results, providing a “study score.” The second step determines the completeness of physicochemical characterization of the

nanomaterial/nanomaterials assessed within the study, providing a “nanomaterial score.”

- ii. Used in the GUIDEnano method

Annex 2 - Compulsory model input parameters for selected risk assessment models

Simplified overview of compulsory model input parameters for the selected HRA models (based on D5.1).

INPUT PARAMETERS	Parameter ontology ID (parent term “information content entity” - IAO_0000030)	Adequate assays	Assay ontology ID (parent term “assay” - OBI_0000070)	Guidenano	LICARA nanosCAN*	NanoSafer CB	Precautionary Matrix	ConExpo Nano	SB4N	MendNano	NanoQSAR	SSWD	ECHA information requirements (ECHA, 2017)
Nanomaterial/Product properties													
Product type / appearance / composition / name	-	NR	NR	X	*	X		X					
Chemical composition	ENM_0000082	ICP-MS	CHMO_0000538										X
		CHN analysis	ENM_8000256										
		XRF	-										
		AAS	-										
		GC-MS	CHMO_0000872										
		HPLC-MS	CHMO_0000543										
		Raman spectroscopy	NPO_1472										
		FTIR	CHMO_0000859										
		NMR	NPO_1470										
Relative (particle) density	-	He-Pycnometry	-	X		X		X	X	X			
Nanoparticle radius	PATO_0002390	TEM SEM	NPO_1430 NPO_1429							X			

		DLS	NPO_1469														
Particle size	NPO_1694	DLS SAXS TEM SEM AFM	NPO_1469 OBI:0002108 NPO_1430 NPO_1429 NPO_1434	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X	X	
Particle size distribution	NPO_1699	TEM	NPO_1430	X		X		X	X	X							
		SEM	NPO_1429														
		AFM	NPO_1434														
		DLS	NPO_1469														
		Sp ICP-MS	-														
		APS	-														
		SMPS	-														
OPC	-																
Particle fractal dimension	-	TEM	NPO_1430												X		
Hamaker constant	BAO_0000587 ¹	Binding constant determination assay	OBI_0001025												X		
Dustiness (for powders)	ENM_9000003	Dustiness assay	ENM_8000225 ²	X	*	X											X
Moisture (for powders)	-	-	-		*												
Molecular weight ³	CHEMINF_000216	HPLC-MS	CHMO_0000543														
Phase ³	-	phase analysis light scattering	NPO_1467														
		XRD	ENM_8000311														
		Raman spectroscopy	NPO_1472														
Crystallinity	NPO_1512	XRD Raman spectroscopy HPLC-MS GC-MS	ENM_8000311 NPO_1472 CHMO_0000543 CHMO_0000872														X
Surface coated	NPO_1962	XPS	NPO_1471			X											
		Oven method + chemical analysis ⁴	-														
		TGA+GC-MS	CHMO_0000860														
		TGA+FTIR	CHMO_0000859														
		HAADF-STEM	-														
Surface chemistry (including composition and reactivity)	ENM_0000090	XPS TGA+GC-MS HPLC-MS	ENM_9000009 CHMO_0000860 CHMO_0000543													X	X ⁵

		Oven method + chemical analysis ⁴ HAADF-STEM	- -														
Particle shape / fibers	NPO_274	TEM SEM AFM	NPO_1430 NPO_1429 NPO_1434	X	*	X		X							X	X	
Specific Surface area	CHEMINF_000247	BET TEM SAXS WAXS	- NPO_1430 OBI_0002108 -	X		X	X	X							X	X	
Surface charge	NPO_1812	Zeta-potential assays	-												X	X	
Crystallinity	NPO_1512	XRD	ENM 8000311	X													
		Raman spectroscopy	NPO_1472														
		HPLC-MS	CHMO_0000543														
		GC-MS	CHMO_0000872														
Purity (%)	UO_0000193 ⁶	Oven method + chemical analysis ⁴	-	X													
		ICP-MS	CHMO_0000538														
		XRF	-														
		AAS	-														
		GC-MS	CHMO_0000872														
		HPLC-MS	CHMO_0000543														
		Raman spectroscopy	NPO_1472														
		FTIR	CHMO_0000859														
NMR	NPO_1470																
Agglomeration	NPO_1966	(Sonication +) DLS ⁷	NPO_1469	X			X	X									
Whether any characterization was performed in the relevant experimental media	-	NR	NR												X		
Viscosity of the liquid (when present in dispersion)	NPO_1857	Viscosimeter	-	X	*												
Percentage of NM in NM-enabled product	-			X	*			X									
Position/location of NM	NPO_1495			X													

in NM-enabled product																				
Interaction																				
Solubility (in water)	PATO:0001536	ICP-MS	CHMO_0000538	X	*	X		X										X		
		Potentiometry	ENM_0000087																	
		Sp ICP-MS																		
Photodegradation	-	-	-																X	
Aerobic degradation	-	-	-																X	
Partition coefficients ³	CHEMINF_000496 ⁸ C20610 ⁸																			
Release rate / production amount	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X												
Dissolution rates	NPO_1955	Chemical analysis of particle free supernatant	-									X	X						X	
Released material	-	-	-	X								X								
Compartment/zone into which the release is emitted	ENVO 00010483			X								X							X	
Emitted quantity	-			X								X								
Agglomeration and/or aggregation rate constants / Attachment efficiencies	NPO_1967	-	-										X	X					X	
Enthalpy of formation	CHEMINF_000241	-	-																X	
Stability (half-life) in physiological matrix/environmental conditions ⁹	UO:0000152 ¹⁰	Phototransformation (air)	-																	
		Hydrolysis	-																	
		Phototransformation (water)	-																	
		Phototransformation (soil)	-																	
		Dispersion stability (water)	-																	
		Abiotic degradability and fate	-																	
Emission to air/(lake) water/sea water/natural soil/agricultural soil/other soil ¹¹	-	NR	NR																	
Matrix																				
Oral toxicity	ENM_0000019	Acute oral toxicity (in vivo)	ENM_0000020			X [#]														X
		Repeated dose	ENM_0000021																	

		aberrations in vitro (OECD 473)																		
		Genotoxicity assay ¹⁵	BAO_0002167																	
		DNA damage assay ¹⁵	ENM_9000017																	
		Transcription profiling assay	OBI_0000424																	
Neurotoxicity	OAE_0001215 ¹⁶	-	-				X [#]													
Immunotoxicity/Inflammation	ENM_0000046 ¹⁷ NPO_1339 ¹⁷	Cytokine secretion in vivo	BAO_0003003																	
		Cytokines in vitro	EFO_0004873																	
		Protein secretion in vitro	-																	
		Polyclonal proliferation in vivo	ENM_8000286																	
		Serum antibodies in vivo	-																	
		Serum cytokines in vivo	ENM_8000290																	
		Blood count in vivo	ENM_8000232																	
		Transcription profiling assay	OBI_0000424																	
Allergy and sensitization	OAE_0000568 ¹⁸ EFO_0005298 ¹⁹ ENM_0000034 ²⁰	Skin sensitization (OECD 406)	-				X [#]													
General toxicity ³	NPO_1338 ²¹	Alamar Blue assay (resazurin)	ENM_8000224																	
		Colony forming efficiency (CFE) assay	ENM_8000235																	
		RT- Impedence adherence cell	ENM_8000289																	
		Impedence flow cytometry	ENM_8000267																	
		LDH release assay	NPO_1709																	
		MTS	ENM_8000275																	
		Neutral red uptake assay	ENM_8000277																	
		Trypan Blue	-																	
Transcription profiling assay	OBI_0000424																			
Potential skin eye/irritation	ENM_0000033 ²² ENM_0000032 ²²	In vitro skin irritation (OECD	-				X [#]													

		439 (skin) 492 (eye))																	
		Acute dermal irritation/corrosion (OECD 404 and OECD 405)	-																
Acute toxicity in fish	ENM_0000010	Fish, Acute toxicity test (OECD 203)	-																X
Acute toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	ENM_0000006	-	-																X
Toxicity to aquatic plants	-	-	-																X
ROS formation	-	H2DCFDA-Probe in vitro	-																
		Glutathione levels	-		X		X												
		DNA oxidation	-																
		NO production in vitro	ENM_8000278																
Catalytic activity	-	Reduction of a dye (crystal violet) ²³	-		X		X												
Redox activity	-	Oxidising properties	-																
		Oxidation reduction potential	-		X		X												X ² ₄
		Oxidative stress assay	BAO_0002168																
Photoreactivity	-	-	-																X
Concentration particles in specific environmental compartment	PATO:0000033 ²⁵	-	-								X	X							
Size particles in specific environmental compartment	PATO:0005015 ²⁶	-	-								X	X							
Density particles in specific environmental compartment	-	-	-								X	X							
Size of natural colloids	-	-	-								X	X							
Density of natural colloids	-	-	-								X	X							
Occupational Exposure Limit (OEL)	-	-	-				X [#]												
System dimensions																			
Room dimensions	-	NR	NR		X	*	X		X										
Distance between source	-	NR	NR			*													

<i>and worker</i>														
<i>Water depth/volume</i>	-	NR	NR						X	X				
<i>Soil density</i>	-	NR	NR						X	X				
<i>Sediment depth</i>	-	NR	NR						X	X				
Conditions														
<i>Ventilation rate in room</i>	-	NR	NR	X	*	X		X						
<i>Activity level in room</i>	-	NR	NR	X		X		X						
<i>Frequency task/use in room</i>	-	NR	NR	X	*	X	X	X						
<i>Humidity in room</i>	-	NR	NR			X								
<i>Duration of process in room</i>	EFO_0000433	NR	NR	X	*	X		X						
<i>Cleaning frequency of workplace</i>	-	NR	NR		*									
<i>Equipment maintenance frequency</i>	-	NR	NR		*									
<i>Number of workers</i>	-	NR	NR	X										
<i>Body weight of workers/consumers</i>	-	NR	NR	X				X						
<i>Total working years of workers/consumers</i>	-	NR	NR	X				X						
<i>Workweeks a year of workers</i>	-	NR	NR	X										
<i>Workdays a week of workers/ days a week consumer usage</i>	-	NR	NR	X	*			X						
<i>Working hours a day of workers / hours per day of use by consumers</i>	-	NR	NR	X	*			X						
<i>Peak concentration</i>	-	NR	NR	X				X						
<i>Long term concentration</i>	-	-	-	X				X						
<i>Total timespan of worker presence</i>	-	NR	NR	X				X						
<i>Worker presence (frequency)</i>	-	NR	NR	X	*			X						
<i>Average duration of worker presence in zone</i>	-	NR	NR	X										
<i>PPE</i>	-	NR	NR		*									
<i>Temperature</i>	NPO_1806	NR	NR						X	X				
<i>Wind speed</i>	-	NR	NR						X	X				
<i>Rainfall</i>	-	NR	NR						X	X				
<i>Water flow rate</i>	UO_0000270	-	-						X	X				
<i>Simulation time</i>	-	NR	NR						X	X				

NR = Not relevant

* Note that LICARA nanoSCAN is a risk benefit tool, which includes (parts of) the other HRA models StoffenManager Nano for occupational risk assessment, and parameters from the Precautionary Matrix for consumer (and environmental) risk assessment. Parameters in LICARA that are compulsory via Stoffenmanager are indicated with an asterix *.

these parameters can be filled in with data for an NM or its nearest analogue bulk material

¹ Refers to “binding constant”, but the Hamaker constant could be included as a child term

² Parent term with several specific assays listed as child terms

³ Required for regulatory assessment (REACH). See ECHA appendix R.7a.

⁴ See NANoREG D2.04

⁵ Hydrophobicity can be derived from surface chemistry (ECHA, 2017)

⁶ The description refers to biomaterials: “A dimensionless percent unit which denotes the homogeneity of a biomaterial. An example of a biomaterial could be an e.g. tumor biopsy.”

⁷ See NANoREG D2.08

⁸ Redundant terms, both are under the same parent term

⁹ Refers to dissolution rate in relevant experimental medium. According to the Swiss Precautionary matrix stability takes into account the stability towards dissolution, chemical or physical transformation, sinterin, sorption, agglomeration/aggregation or particle degradation or conversion into metabolic products.

¹⁰ Refers to half life and is defined as: “Typically applied to the half life of radioactive atoms but also applicable to any other situation where the population is of molecules of diminishing concentration or activity. A time unit which represents the period over which the activity or concentration of a specified chemical or element falls to half its original activity or concentration.”

¹¹ Parameters not necessarily compulsory for running the model (and to be retrieved from the nano-databases), however, still key parameters for model testing.

¹² Parent term “information content entity” rather than “assay”

¹³ Reproductive toxicity

¹⁴ Developmental toxicity

¹⁵ These generic terms can function as parent terms in the ontology, under which more specific assays are listed

¹⁶ Listed under parent term “adverse event”, which are potentially relevant to AOPs, useful for relating assays that address potential future AOP-based refinements of the RA models

¹⁷ These two ontology IDs are redundant and fall under the same parent term “toxicological endpoint”

¹⁸ allergy

¹⁹ allergic sensitization measurement

²⁰ skin sensitization

²¹ The ID refers to toxicity, which is a parent term to many of the toxicological assays in the table

²² Listed under the parent term “toxicological endpoint”. There are redundant terms listed under “adverse event”. Ontology IDs listed under “adverse event” are relevant to AOPs, which can be related to assays that address potential future AOP-based refinements of the RA models

²³ According to the Swiss Precautionary Matrix

²⁴ Covers the ECHA information requirement surface reactivity (biological reactivity)

²⁵ Defined as “A quality inhering in a substance by virtue of the amount of the bearer's there is mixed with another substance.” Different environmental compartments could be added in the ontology under this parent term

²⁶ Refers to “tapered size” and is defined as “A size quality inhering in an entity or set of entities in which size increases or decreases along

the extent of the entity or set."

Annex 3 - Minimum information checklists for physicochemical characterization data of NM

*Minimum information checklist for physical-chemical characterization data of NMs (based on minimal compulsory entries for physicochemical characterization data in D5.1) - caLIBRAte version 1**

Physical-chemical characterization	Ontology ID(s) (parent term "quality" BFO_0000019)	Adequate assay(s)	Assay ontology ID (parent term "assay" - OBI_0000070)	Description ¹
Composition	CHEMINF_000230	ICP-MS CHN analysis XRF AAS GC-MS HPLC-MS Raman spectroscopy FTIR NMR	CHMO_0000538 ENM_8000256 - - CHMO_0000872 CHMO_0000543 NPO_1472 CHMO_0000859 NPO_1470	chemical composition, substance,
Atomic structure / crystallinity	NPO_1512	XRD Raman spectroscopy HRTEM UV-vis	ENM_8000311 NPO_1472 NPO_1451 -	Atomic structure for naming substance
Size/size range	NPO_1694	DLS SAXS TEM WAXD WAXS	NPO_1469 OBI:0002108 NPO_1430 - -	The physical dimensions of a particle: for spherical particles it is their diameter. For irregularly shaped particles it is the diameter of the equivalent sphere that has the same volume as a particle. Also includes physical state of a sample. ¹
Size distribution	NPO_1697 ³ ENM_8000292 ³	TEM SEM AFM DLS Sp ICP-MS APS SMPS OPC	NPO_1430 NPO_1429 NPO_1434 NPO_1469 - - - -	A list of values which define the relative amounts of particles present, sorted according to size – including modality, peak magnitude, minimum and maximum.
Purity	UO_0000193 ⁴	ICP-MS	CHMO:0000538	Fraction of the intended substance

		XRF AAS GC-MS HPLC-MS Raman spectroscopy FTIR NMR	- - CHMO_0000872 CHMO_0000543 NPO_1472 CHMO_0000859 NPO_1470	within a manufactured material – also includes identity and amount of any contaminants.
Shape/morphology	NPO_274	TEM SEM AFM	NPO_1430 NPO_1429 NPO_1434	A geometric description of the extremities of a nanomaterial.
Surface chemistry	ENM_0000090	XPS TGA+GC-MS HPLC-MS Oven method + chemical analysis ⁵ HAADF-STEM	ENM_9000009 CHMO_0000860 CHMO_0000543 - -	The chemical nature of the outermost layer of a nanomaterial: reactivity, hydrophobicity, coating, and functionalization
Agglomeration/aggregation state	NPO_1966 ⁶ NPO_1967 ⁷	(Sonication +) DLS (Sonication +) TEM (Sonication +) SEM	NPO_1469 NPO_1430 NPO_1429	The extent to which a group of particles, affected by attractive forces, form groups or clusters. Agglomerate: A group of particles held together by weak forces such as van der Waals forces, some electrostatic forces and or surface tension. Aggregate: A group of particles held together by strong forces such as those associated with covalent or metallic bonds.
Surface area	CHEMINF_000247	BET TEM SAXS	- NPO_1430 OBI:0002108	The quantity of accessible surface of a nanomaterial expressed as a mass-specific surface area or as a volume-specific surface area where the total area quantity has been normalized either to the sample's mass or to a volume. (e.g. BET ⁸ (surface area))
Surface charge	NPO_1812	Zeta-potential measurements Electrophoresis	- NPO_1418	The electric charge present at the surface of the nanomaterial.
Stability (solubility, dissolution rate)	C54072 ⁹ PATO:0001536 ¹⁰ NPO_1955 ¹¹	ICP-MS Potentiometry Sp ICP-MS	CHMO_0000538 ENM_0000087 -	The measure of a system is in its lowest energy state or chemical equilibrium with its environment. Include solubility, and the rate of material release through dissolution.

*Referred to as version 1, since refinements are expected due to increasing scientific knowledge on the key overarching properties of NM

¹(Ostraat et al. 2013, Bakker and Noorlander 2014)

² The regulatory definition is related to the minimum diameter and minimum diameter size-distribution by number (not mass).

³ Redundant – both are under the same parent term

⁴ The description refers to biomaterials... “A dimensionless percent unit which denotes the homogeneity of a biomaterial. An example of a biomaterial could be an e.g. tumor biopsy.”

⁵ See NANoREG D2.04

⁶ Agglomeration

⁷ Aggregation

⁸ BET = Brunauer, Emmett and Teller

⁹ Stability

¹⁰ Solubility

¹¹ Dissolution

Annex 4 - Minimum information checklists for toxicity data

Minimum information checklist for human in vivo and in vitro toxicity data of NMs (based on minimal compulsory entries for in vivo and in vitro toxicity data in D5.1).

Category	In vivo toxicity data parameter	Ontology ID (relevant parent term*)	In vitro toxicity data parameter	Ontology ID (relevant parent term*)
Test substance	Physicochemical characterization (see Annex 3) under biologically relevant conditions; incl. type of used medium)	ENM_9000015 ¹	Physicochemical characterization (see Annex 3) under biologically relevant conditions; incl. type of used medium	ENM_9000015 ¹
	Information on method of suspension (type of used medium, preparation of stock solution, nominal concentration)	-	Information on method of suspension (type of used medium, preparation of stock solution, nominal concentration)	-
	Description of origin/source of NP	-	Description of origin/source of NP	-
Test subject	Species ²	OBI_0100026 ³	Cell type Species/source of cells	-
	Strain	-	Culture type (primary cell culture, cultured cell line, genetically engineered, co-cultured, 3-dimensional)	EFO_0000322 ⁴
	Age	PATO_0000011	Growth rate/ doubling time	PATO:0001492 ⁵
			Passage number	EFO_0007061
			Mycoplasma testing	-
			Morphological appearance	-
			Authenticity (genotyping)	EFO_0000513 ⁶
	Body weight	EFO_0004338		
	Sex	-		
	Housing and feed conditions	-		

Methods	Toxicological endpoint and type of assay	ENM_0000018 ⁷ OBI_0000070	Toxicological endpoint and type of assay	ENM_0000018 OBI_0000070
	Number of test subjects/animals ²	NR	Number of replicates	NR
	Number of treatment groups	NR	Number of treatment groups	NR
	Data on the administered dose/concentration ²	-	Data on the administered dose/concentration ²	-
	Frequency and duration of dosing ²	PATO_0000044 ⁸ EFO_0000433 ⁹	Frequency and duration of dosing ²	PATO_0000044 EFO_0000433
	Route of administration ²	C83121		
	Detailed description of experimental measurements and procedures	C25365 ¹⁰	Detailed description of experimental measurements and procedures.	C25365
	Appropriate negative/positive controls ²	-	Appropriate negative/positive controls ²	-
	Assessment of interference	-	Assessment of interference	-

*The relevant parent term in the ontology under which child terms potentially useful for annotation of metadata can be found

NR – Not relevant

¹ Currently under the parent term “cell viability assay” – could rather be placed under that terms parent term “bioassay”

² Related to red criteria in the ToxRTool

³ Refers to organism, could be a parent term for species

⁴ Refers to cell line

⁵ Currently refers to the growth of a whole organ/tissue

⁶ genotype

⁷ This is a parent term with relevant toxicity endpoints as child terms – the child terms should be used when describing which toxicity endpoint was assessed

⁸ Frequency

⁹ Duration

¹⁰ Parent term “assay”

Minimum information checklist for ecotoxicity data (based on minimal compulsory entries for ecotoxicity data in D5.1).

Category	Ecotoxicity data parameter	Ontology ID (relevant parent term*)
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Test substance	Physicochemical characterization (under biologically relevant conditions, also behaviour in test media and stock solutions, over time; see Annex 3) ¹	ENM_9000015
	Information on method of suspension (type of used medium, preparation of stock solution, nominal concentration)	-
	Description of origin/source of NP	-
Test subject	Information on test subject: - Species? Other? ¹	-
	Information on relevant test media: ¹ - Air (temperature?, other?) - Water (alkalinity, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, hardness, ionic fraction, pH, salinity, dissolved and total organic carbon, temperature, ionic strength) - Soil (type, concentration of heavy metals, total organic carbon, moisture, pH, void volume, total weight of volume)	ENVO_00010483 ²
	Test location: field/laboratory	-
Methods	Number of replicates ¹	NR
	Number of treatment groups ¹	NR
	Data on the administered dose or concentration present in media ¹	-
	Frequency and duration of dosing ¹	PATO_0000044 ³ EFO_0000433 ⁴
	Detailed description of experimental measurements and procedures	C25365
	Appropriate negative/positive controls	-
	Assessment of interference	-
	Data on fate and transport of NP in the environment.	-

*The relevant parent term in the ontology under which child terms potentially useful for annotation of metadata can be found

NR – Not relevant

¹ Related to “red criteria” in NanoCRED (based on the ToxRTool)

² Refers to environmental material - The child terms refer to air, water and soil, which further refer to different types of each media

³ Frequency

⁴ Duration

Minimum information checklist for occupational and consumer exposure data (based on input and expertise from partners working in WP6).

Category	Human exposure: occupational and consumer exposure parameter	Ontology ID (relevant parent term*)
Test substance	Physical-chemical characteristics (see Annex 3)	ENM_9000015
	Type of product (~100% nano or intermediate/final product; incl. weight fraction of nano in product)	-
	Physical form of nanomaterial/product (liquid, powder, solid matrix)	-

	In case of powders: dustiness category (e.g. very high, high, medium, low).	ENM_9000003
	In case of liquid: viscosity (e.g. low, medium, high)	NPO_1857 ¹
	Product category (car product, pesticides, landscape/yard, personal care) and preferable product type (facial crème, deodorant etc.) or even better specific information like brand.	-
Test subject	Exposed body area (cm ²)	-
	Measurement location (breathing zone, source, distance from source/person)	-
	Amount of nanomaterial/nanoproduct used.	-
	Route of exposure	-
	Location (inside/outside and size of room in m ³)	-
Methods	Description of exposure scenario (room dimensions, ventilation rate)	-
	Activity/application method (spraying, brushing, pouring, etc.) or description of use product (amount of product used, release rate)	CHEBI_33232 ²
	Frequency and duration of exposure	PATO_0000044 EFO_0000433
	Used exposure controls (Local & General Exhaust Ventilation Monitoring ; LEV/GEV, personal protection equipment; PPEs etc.) and preferably type of LEV/GEV, PPE used and efficiency (air changes per hour).	-
	Background concentration	-
	Activity level in room (Describes the environment in which the activity, exposure or release of nanoparticles occurs.)	-
	Detailed description of experimental measurements and procedures	C25365
	Climate conditions (temperature and relative humidity)	-
	Description of secondary sources (diesel engines, cigarette smoke, welding, busy road, etc.	-

*The relevant parent term in the ontology under which child terms potentially useful for annotation of metadata can be found

¹ Refers to viscosity value

² Refers to application, which is related to functionality, on which an ontology has been developed and is being analysed/integrated with the eNanoMapper ontology in NanoReg2

Minimum information checklist for environmental fate data (based on input and expertise from partners working in WP6).

Environmental exposure		Ontology ID (relevant parent term*)
Test substance	Physicochemical characteristics (see Annex 3)	ENM_9000015
	Particle fractal dimension	-
	Nanoparticle radius	PATO_0002390
	Speciation of concentrations (free nanoparticles, bound to other environmental nanoparticles, bound to bigger environmental particles)	-
Process	Attachment efficiency	-

properties	Dissolution rate	NPO_1955
	Emission to relevant media	-
Test subject	For each measured compartment: temperature , plus for: Soil/sediment: soil depth, soil density Air: ambient aerosol density, number of aerosols, wind speed, rainfall Water: size of natural colloids, water depth/volume, water flow rate	ENVO_00010483 ¹
Methods	Measured concentrations in relevant compartments	PATO_0000033
	Description of measurement method including: - controls/blanks - number of replicates	C25365

*The relevant parent term in the ontology under which child terms potentially useful for annotation of metadata can be found

1 Refers to environmental material - The child terms refer to air, water and soil, which further refer to different types of each media

